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THE IMPOSED POST-TRAUMATIC STRESS DISORDER BY COMMUNITIES AND ITS IMPACT ON FEMALES: BEING WOMAN IN TURKEY AND IRAN

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the physical and psychological violence stemming from the patriarchal system—the common ground for both the women governed by Turkey’s secular hierarchy and women governed by Iran’s Islamic Sharia system—is discussed. The gender roles of women, the struggle of women for survival in patriarchal societies under Sharia, women’s mental conditions, the violence women have been subjected to, issues such as the normalization of violence, and female rights are also emphasized. Due to the policy of equality between genders in societies, violation and the advocacy of male domination in the realm of femicide should be studied. In both communities, Turkey and Iran, women are restricted from developing their capacities. While their freedom is restricted, they are obliged to live with eventuating psychology. The patriarchal system causes all kinds of violence, abuse, discrimination against women, and restrictions on their right to live independently. Violence, which is one of humanity’s biggest problems, is partitioned within itself while the outcome is always the same. This study is focused on women living in Turkey and Iran when addressing physical and psychological violence they have been subjected to for years, and society’s ideological dilemmas are also investigated. The mobbings and post-traumatic stress disorders that women are subjected to and molded to society are discussed by following the DSM-5 diagnostic criteria manually. This study emphasizes female perception as semi-individual after restrictions imposed on personal freedom by the moral police in Iran and by the public in Turkey. Discussing women’s place and the neglected psychology of women in society, attention was also drawn to the normalization of the traumas they experienced—by regarding the facts they experienced throughout their lives. By defining all types of violence against women, the stages of violence, society’s attitude towards violence, and the perpetrators’ profiles, women suffered pressure is psychologically examined. The cause of mental illnesses in women who are suffering from violence is exposing their experienced violence. Depending on the situation in which women are in, the issues of normalization are declared precisely. Psychological violence—as abrasive and damaging as physical violence—which deals with two different cultures is studied in this article.

Keywords: *Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder, Psychological Violence, Physical Violence, Women’s Rights, Gender*

INTRODUCTION

To fulfill patriarchal expectations, women are subjected to all kinds of abuse that are normalized by the target society. In patriarchal societies, women are segregated, and the masculine community prevents women from defending their rights, where they are subjected to various psychological, physical, sexual, and economic abuses. The mental health of women seriously affects the extent of suffered abuse. Normalities that are accepted as a result of cultural differences cause gender discrimination. Although equality of gender is announced before the laws, women's rights are sometimes taken away decisively. Women who plan to be intervened in their career are subjected to a great mobbing by the patriarchal society in all forms of sexual orientation to their physical appearance, education rights, and income. Depending on the abuses they have suffered, their mental health is affected.

WOMEN AND ABUSE

The word abuse is defined as exploitation in the dictionary, and the development of this destructive and corrosive act over gender is called gender abuse. All of the emotional, mental, physical, and economic actions that take place against the woman's consent may exploit, prevent, or restrict the woman. These are considered as a type of abuse—since the masculine is seen as superior in the patriarchal society—and women concede to it at any stage of their lives. Women's objectification or being inferior—compared to men—are among the instances of normalization of gender discrimination and abuse. Females become a victim of sex discrimination in the patriarchal society, where emotional abuse, as an invisible type of abuse, is not noticed by society. Emotional abuse caused by a woman's emotional support and disregard for her needs—such as being belittled, punished, leaving alone, threatened and rejected—is often considered as usual. Emotional abuse is not accepted as physical abuse when society ignores it or accepts it as a norm.

Emotional abuse, which includes verbal and psychological abuse, may cause a lack of self-confidence, depression, social anxiety, and traumas for the exposed individuals. It may take time for people who have been subjected to emotional abuse to realize it; since they are faced with a feeling of humiliation, and they may hesitate to share it with people in their immediate vicinity. The situation of women who have been subjected to economic abuse is not considered differently. Their duty is restricted; they are prevented from promoting, or their husbands, fathers, or friends confiscate their income. Gender discrimination in the form of unequal work distribution is observed in many workplaces. According to Özyaydınlık (2014), gender-based labor division differentiates women and men and affects their access to social resources unequally. Sometimes personal expenses are impeded, and society's perspective on economic abuse can be rooted in idioms such as "try to do a man's job." Economic abuse that is often encountered is a significant attack on personal rights, and it is a type of domestic violence while the man who works and cares for her family expects his wife to serve him at home.

According to Parlaktuna (2010), gender-based occupational discrimination, which is directly related to the development of countries' economic, social and cultural structures, is a reflection of the problems stemming from the country's inadequate economic and socio-cultural structure. Economic and emotional abuse that causes stereotype helplessness causes emotional inadequacy. Discrimination can occur in every country with significant differences in jobs and privacy of males and females. Job segregation, according to countries, can be evaluated as women's or men's jobs. Situations such as stress, anxiety, depression, and inadequacy can be visited in people who are exposed to abuse. After the Islamic Revolution of the Republic of Iran in 1979, women's legal rights were abandoned. According to Aşık (2006), the abolition of post-revolution coeducation and the necessity of a headscarf has led to

different gender inequality concepts in textbooks. Thereby, duty division in the family and public spheres has been made in the realm of gender discrimination. (p. 151)

In Iran, women's freedom to travel abroad is in line with the permission given by the father or the spouse. Women—whose freedom of expression is abolished—do not have the right to get divorced. In inheritance shares, they can receive half the property of a man. Besides, when they witness a situation, the testimony of two women under the Islamic rules of Iran—governed by Sharia—is equated with a man's testimony. A woman is seen as half a man before the law. A woman whose right to divorce has been taken can continue or be terminated at the man's request. In Iran, where the pressure to dress according to Islamic conditions continues, women are also prohibited from watching football matches. Women who want to be united to make their voices heard are stopped by moral police, subjected to violence, or taken to court.¹ In 2019, when Seher Hedayari, who opposed the ban, wore a man's outfit and entered a soccer match, she was caught and detained. After she was released conditionally, she set herself on fire in front of the Tehran revolutionary court, but could not be saved.

In his study, Kahraman (2014) explained that women who are tied up because of Iran's peculiar conditions are crushed under the weight of structures settled based on gender inequality, which is exposed to them. (Hero, 2014, p. 113) Although the Republic of Turkey is a country governed by civil laws, however, because it is a patriarchal society, abuse against women and domestic violence cannot be prevented. According to Karanisoğlu & Oskay (1995), women worldwide, due to their gender, are systematically subjected to inhumane procedures such as violence, sexual harassment, and domestic rape. Every day we encounter abuse and women murders in the news, media, and the press that now became an open wound of Turkish society. Patriarchal society tries to make people adopt the sayings such as "spare the rod and spoil the child," "do not take a stick from the back of the woman, and the body of the woman," and women who have been subjected to sexual abuse cannot share their close circles, as they are ashamed of the abuse they have been subjected to.

Incest relationships—such as child brides—are currently the subject of many TV series and movies, while this sexual abuse is equal to rape. Women's rights defenders advocate this rape as a massacre and violent crime rather than sexual abuse (Russell, 1984). Sexual abuse includes all kinds of sexual assault that occurs without the person's consent, such as touching, forced sexual partnerships, taking obscene photos, blackmailing, performing sexually explicit conversations, performing unwanted acts during sexual intercourse, having unprotected sexual intercourse, forcing abortion/preventing abortion, materials or sex toys that may damage the genitals. Women who have been subjected to sexual abuse also experience many physical and psychological illnesses; women who have sexual intercourse before marriage are not preferred to get married in Turkey. When women who have been sexually abused before marriage are forced due to the social pressure on virginity, they cannot share the situation with anyone, while most of the sexual abuse is committed by men who are close to abused women.

By staying silent, abuse will be continued. Societies that patriarchal society defines virginity as a symbol of honor cannot react to the abuse they are exposed to women. According to Yüksel (1996), all women who have experienced rape—regardless of whether they are married or single or had/did not have a sexual experience—should be treated within the system of the same values. Married women are also not considered as the victim of sexual abuse by their husbands. In her interview to *Hürriyet* newspaper with expatriate Ayşe Tükrükçü, who is known as the owner of a hug life restaurant, Ayşe Arman (2015) says the story of Tükrükçü has made a significant impact on society. Ayşe Tükrükçü, who was raped by her uncle at the age of 9, stated that she was subjected to sexual abuse and physical abuse and that

¹ <https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/dunya/mavi-kiz-kendini-yakti-41327384>

she was taken from her family at the age of 11 and given to an orphanage due to the cover-up of domestic sexual abuse. After her marriage, Ayşe Tükrükü, who was sold to a brothel by her husband, stated that she had sex with 70 people a day. (Arman, 2015)

In Iran, sex traffick is allowed in accordance with Islamic rules of Sharia. They make a short-term religious marriage through the Muta wedding, which takes place daily, hourly, or weekly, and carry out the sex trade following Islamic rules. The muta wedding, which is also performed for a certain fee, is an accepted marriage type in Iran. According to the *Ibtikar* newspaper's news, the Muta wedding, which has recently received as a significant reaction, is considered legal in Iran². Domestic sexual abuse is often hidden or ignored. It is known that women who have been subjected to psychological, economic, and sexual abuse are also exposed to physical abuse. Physical abuse is a type of abuse that includes the physical force and is carried out with the aim of physical injury. Hitting, slapping, punching, trying to choke, throwing any object, using hurtful objects, and torturing are also contained. In 2014, in Isfahan, Iran, at different times, four women were attacked, causing the women to be physically injured because they did not dress according to Islamic values³. The use of acidic substances, which males frequently perpetrate as a punishment method, damages the physical integrity of the individual, or causes death. The frequent acid substance used in Iran is also repeated in Turkey. Physical violence can result in death, which is a crime against humanity. A great majority of people react to physical abuse while at the same time, hesitating to intervene. The university student who decided to stop the physical abuse caused his death. During the brawl, he attempted to intervene in a criminal's act named who used violence against Özgür Duran. Later, 20-year-old Kadir Şeker (2020) was arrested for 'deliberate killing⁴.'

Even if people want to intervene in abusing events, but society's fear of harming or being harmed prevents them from reacting. In the Islamic Republic of Iran, people refrain from reacting to the events taking place due to the fear of moral police. The horror of the punishments in Iran prevents people from making their voices. People are also prevented from defending their rights in connection with severe punishments such as whip, stoning, amputation, and retaliation. The methods of the applied punishments are divided into men and women; in the stone to death punishment, which is a form of the death penalty based on the stoning of adulterers, and it differs in its application to men and women. When men are only buried up to their waist, women must be buried deeper⁵. In the penal system used for killing, the person is stoned to death by his family and others in a way that will be subjected to torture. While men buried up to their waist have a higher chance of escaping, women cannot escape from this punishing method. This punishment system—where the fleeing person is believed to be justified—is inhuman. Women who are sentenced to stoning are murdered in front of people. An Iranian human rights defender and writer, Golrokh Ebrahimi Iraee's article on stoning, was sentenced to prison for "anti-system propaganda" and "denigrating the sacred values of Islam," and it was stated that she would be executed⁶.

² <https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/dunya/iranda-cep-telefonundan-muta-nikahi-40144033>

³ https://www.bbc.com/turkce/multimedya/2014/10/141020_iran_asitli_saldiri

⁴ <https://www.bbc.com/turkce/haberler-turkiye-51427492>

⁵ <https://www.cnnturk.com/2010/dunya/07/02/iranda.yine.taslanarak.oldurulecek.bir.kadin/582063.0/index.htm>
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⁶ <https://www.sozcu.com.tr/2016/dunya/son-dakika-iranda-recm-hakkinda-yazan-yazara-hapis-cezasi-1432936/>

MENTAL ILLNESSES AFTER ABUSE

It is common for people exposed to abuse to have physical and mental illnesses. The fact that abuse is an abrasive and destructive act causes trauma in the imposed person. It is known that traumas that vary from person to person, and other mental illnesses are also seen in people who experienced it. One measure of abuse is as follows: even if the person is not directly exposed to abuse, they may experience trauma as a result of the acts they witness. According to Özgen & Aydın (1999), individuals' genetic characteristics, physical structure, psychological background and motivation for that situation, and coping mechanisms with specific stressors are different. Therefore, the prevalence of Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) varies. (p.34)

Trauma's background is as old as humanity's history. It was first defined by including physical traumas. In the following years, the first research on the psychological effects of trauma was carried out on patients with hysteria by the French Neurologist Jean-Martin Charcot (Veith, 1977, p.9). Post-traumatic stress can occur depending on the types of stress disorder and abuse, natural disasters, sudden death or injuries, accidents, or childhood. It is accompanied by an unexpected fear, sadness, or despair. Psychological reactions to negative experiences are a subject that many researchers have included in their research. (Van der Kolk, et al.; 1996, Fischer & Riedesser, 1999; Maercker, 2005) Post-traumatic stress disorder may vary from person to person, and the same traumatic effects may not be expected to influence every person equally. Studies have also mentioned the psychological reactions that occur due to life-threatening events. (Spurrell & McFarlane, 1995; Van der Kolk et al., 1996; O'Brian, 1998)

It is possible to relate to other mental illnesses with post-traumatic stress disorder. According to Sungur (1999), social support is an essential factor that determines whether acute PTSD becomes chronic or not. As the chronicity of the trauma may vary from person to person, the social support they receive is also essential. People with post-traumatic stress disorder develop chronic post-traumatic stress disorder when they are not supported, and the traumas experienced by those who attempt suicide are more significant than other people. (Blaauw et al., 2002; Goldney et al., 2000; Roy, 2001; Statham et al., 1998) People can constantly feel and react to the same event, and dissociative returns are seen in 8-13% of traumatized individuals as re-experiencing the traumatic event without any unconsciousness (Burstein, 1985). Breslau et al. (1997) also hypothesized that 80-100% of people had experienced a traumatic event, at least once in their life, since they started to survive. (Breslau et al., 1997)

They may experience sleep disturbances, loss or increase in appetite, palpitations, nausea/vomiting, panic attacks, anxiety, stress, or they may attempt to not want to remember the incident and cover it up. Beers et al. (1999) was defined it as a disorder that involves recalling after a traumatic event. It evokes emotions such as intense fear and helplessness, thus, avoiding stimuli related to trauma. The longer the treatment initiation process is delayed, the longer the person's recovery process will be completed. People need to get psychiatric and psychological support. One of the main reasons for late initiation of treatment may be the fear of hearing the event or continuing the action causing the trauma. Apart from this, it may be due to financial insufficiency or the belief that there is no treatment. One of the most common mental illnesses after trauma is anxiety. It occurs with symptoms such as boredom, excitement, stress, bad feelings, hand, foot tremors, and excessive sweating. According to Türkçapar (2004), anxiety disorders include; panic attack, agoraphobia, panic disorder without agoraphobia, agoraphobia with panic disorder, agoraphobia without panic disorder, specific phobia, social phobia, obsessive-compulsive disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder, acute stress disorder, a generalized anxiety disorder that is defined as anxiety disorder due to the general medical condition and anxiety disorders.

Depression can often be realized through post-traumatic stress disorders, such as depressed mood, pessimism, suicidal thoughts, lack of pleasure, lack of self-confidence, appetite, and sleep disorders. Karamustafaloğlu & Yumrukçal (2011) defined depression as unhappiness and a kind of the usual reactions people give to adverse developments. Women subjected to violence, as are not talking about domestic abuse and sexual abuse, hardly expressed or could not tell about their experiences. The abuse remains hidden and causes the trauma to continue. (Avin, 2002) Eskin et al. (2006) commented that the nature of suicide-related attitudes might prevent some suicide cases within the dominant cultural understanding. The fact that Fatma Sariaslan, who could not withstand the physical violence by her husband—although she had a protection order in 2016—committed suicide, is an example of the suicidal attempts of an abused woman. Psychiatric disorders are one of the most important causes of suicides, and it is known that social, psychological, and economic factors play a significant role in suicide attempts. (Eskin, et al., 2006)

WOMEN'S SOLIDARITY

Turkish society is exposed to stop the abuse and murder of women, and there was founded many associations and platforms. One of the best known of them, Mor Çatı, settled in Istanbul in 1987 and supported by 2500 women who were saying, “We do not want the paradise where the beating broke out,” “There is no rightful beating.” In 1990, Mor Çatı Women’s Asylum Foundation was established, and they formed a telephone network where women could receive legal support from the institute. Also, KADAV, the women’s solidarity foundation, was officially established in 2001 and provides consultancy support upon the applications of women subjected to violence. Social anxiety disorders in DSM-IV, which is the diagnostic and numerical handbook of mental disorders. It was defined as a feeling of constant fear and anxiety with realizing a society or action that may be ashamed, and it will turn into a panic attack due to this reaction. (DSM-IV, 1994)

In Iran, women who are opposed to the obligation to cover their heads after the Islamic revolution of 1979 established The White Wednesdays after the protests and movements to support Iran’s female rights were blocked and prohibited by the revolutionary guards. Also, My Stealthy Freedom, launched by journalist Masih Alinejad on social media, shares women’s photos and videos on social media with #WhiteWednesdays hashtag to state women’s reactions on the defense of freedom. The women participating in the movement are activists who called to wear white covers every Wednesday. In The White Wednesdays movement, women shake the head coverings imposed on them every Wednesday by wearing their scarves on a stick. In this movement, which is supported by many in Iran, women wear white headscarves, while men who want to support women wear white bracelets. Recently, men who are against violence and abuse also support women in these protests. The men participating in the protests share the projects prepared for women’s voices on social media to support Iranian women.

Since there is a restriction on social media use in Iran, the public may not be aware of the vast majority of the actions taken to communicate or make their voices heard on social media. Access to the world’s most frequently used websites, such as Facebook, YouTube, and Twitter is banned. While the Islamic regime imposes severe sanctions on internet use, it also restricts people’s ability to express their freedom of thought and exerts psychological pressure. While the society is prevented from expressing itself, criticizing the system and communicating with the world in line with all restrictions is necessary. The fact that Twitter, which politicians actively use, is prohibited to the public is significant discrimination. The power given to moral police has become one of the biggest fears of women living in Iran. In a report published in 2018, a woman sitting in the park was beaten to death by the moral police for allegedly violating the laws applicable to the headscarf. The incident in which the opponents are described as a “small problem” on social media is a significant crime against humanity. (AA., 2018)

It is possible to experience constant fear, anxiety, panic attacks, and social anxiety disorders with the oppression that women living in Iran are exposed to.

A university student in Turkey, Ceren Özdemir, was brutally murdered in front of her house's door in 2019. Afterward, many women living in Turkey, while walking down the street, said they were uneasy due to brutal behaviors in society⁷. The feeling of being chased, which is one of the symptoms of some mental illnesses, has traumatized the society in connection with the events experienced. The feeling of being followed, which is one of the symptoms of mental illnesses, has traumatized the society in connection with the events experienced. In Turkey, when the van driver brutally raped and killed a psychology student Özgecan Aslan, Nihat Dogan, the artist wrote via social media, "You wear miniskirts, you undress; so, you cannot shout loudly to perverts that corrupt the harassed secular system." Not only he defended the patriarchal system, but he considered women as sexual objects⁸. It was a shameful attempt by an artist to normalize the rape of women due to their appearance. After Özgecan Aslan's death, the Women's Solidarity Center (ÖKDM) was established by İzmir Buca Municipality in memory of Özgecan, where they provide psychological and legal services for women⁹.

CONCLUSION

This study deals with all kinds of abuse that women are subjected to in Middle Eastern countries, which are governed by a patriarchal system, and the traumas they experience. Women who make up half of society—subjected to abuse and mental illnesses—should be revealed together. The abuses women are subjected to—both within and outside the family—are similar to other women who continue their lives with learned helplessness. By accepting its existence, it was concluded that a considerable number of men had supported women's struggles to support women. It is a crime against humanity that the patriarchal system wants to enslave women and take away women's existing legal and vital rights. The patriarchal system is one of the main reasons for the victimization of women.

This article aims to deal with the experiences of women who were killed and subjected to all kinds of violence, support women's victimization, realize the psychological effects of abuse, and share the voice of women exposed to abuse. The suffered abuse by women at home, on the street, in public vehicles, and in workplaces caused post-traumatic stress disorder and, consequently, anxiety, depression, social anxiety, panic attack, and obsessive-compulsive disorders. The trauma experienced is among the normals of the patriarchal society, causes a delay in the initiation of therapy and makes it chronic. It increases the number of people who are exposed to abuse and attempted suicide or have suicidal thoughts; however, this situation is different for individuals who receive social support from their immediate vicinity. Keeping silent to abuse is somehow participating in the process. It is an issue that will embarrass not the exposed person who suffers the upcoming of the experienced trauma, but also the abuser.

⁷ <https://www.sozcu.com.tr/2019/gundem/genc-balerin-evinin-onunde-bicaklandi-yasan-savasi-veriyor-5487930/>

⁸ <https://www.citationmachine.net/bibliographies/5939d161-35e3-4377-9c46-64954ad574e4>

⁹ <https://www.evrensel.net/haber/392916/ozgecan-aslan-kadin-danisma-merkezi-bucali-kadinlara-destek-sagliyor>

REFERENCES

- AA. (2016, July 13). İnan'ında cep telefonundan' muta nikahı'. Retrieved October 10, 2020, from <https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/dunya/iranda-cep-telefonundan-muta-nikahi-40144033>
- American Psychiatric Association (1994). *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders: Versison IV (DSM-IV)*, Washington D.C., American Psychiatric Association.
- Ahlak polisinden başörtü dayığı!: Gazete Vatan. (2018, April 21). Retrieved October 01, 2020, from <http://www.gazetevatan.com/ahlak-polisinden-basortu-dayagi--1160196-dunya/>
- Avina, C. & O'Donohue, W. (2002). Sexual harassment and PTSD: Is Sexual Harassment Diagnosable Trauma?, *Journal of Traumatic Stress, 15*, pp. 69-75.
- Arman, A. (May 24, 2015). Ayşe Tükrükçü'nün akıllara durgunluk veren hikâyesi, *Hürriyet*, Retrieved October 01, 2020, from <https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/yazarlar/ayse-arman/ayse-tukrukcu-nun-akillara-durgunluk-veren-hik-yesi-29088792>
- Aşık, M. O. (2006). 1851 Yılından Günümüze İnan Eğitim Sisteminin Beklenmeyen Sonuçları, *Sosyoloji Dergisi, 16*, pp. 137-158.
- Blaauw, E., Arensman, E. , Kraaij, V, et al. (2002). Traumatic life events and suicide risk among jail inmates: the influence of types of events, time period and significant others. *J Trauma Stress, 15*, pp. 9-16.
- Beers, M. H. & Berkow, R. (1999). *The Merck Manual of Diagnosis and Therapy; 17. edition*, West Point: John Wiley & Sons, pp. 1503-99
- Burstein, A. (1985). Posttravmatik flashbacks, dream disturbances and mental imagery. *J Clin Psychiatry, 46*, pp.374-378
- Breslau, N. , Davis, G. C., Andreski, P. et al. (1997). Sex differences in post-traumatic stress disorder. *Arch Gen Psychiatry; 54(11)*, pp. 1044-1048.
- Eskin, M., Akoğlu, A., & Uygur, B. (2006). Ayaktan Tedavi Edilen Psikiyatri Hastalarında Travmatik Yaşam Olayları ve Sorun Çözme Becerileri: İntihar Davranışıyla İlişkisi, *Turkish Journal of Psychiatry*, pp. 266-275.
- Fischer, G. & Riedesser, P. (1999). *Lehrbuch der Psychotraumatologie*. München. Reinhardt.
- Genç balerin Ceren Özdemir evinin önünde bıçaklandı! Yaşam savaşını kaybetti. (2019, December 04). Retrieved October 10, 2020, from <https://www.sozcu.com.tr/2019/gundem/genc-balerin-evinin-onunde-bicaklandi-yasan-savasi-veriyor-5487930/>
- Başbakanlık Kadın Statüsü ve Sorunları Genel Müdürlüğü, (2000a), Kadın İstihdamı İçin Yeni Perspektifler ve Kadın İşgücüne Muhtemel Talep, (Proje Yürütücüsü: Doç.Dr. Şemsa ÖZAR), Nisan 2000, Ankara: Cem.
- Goldney, R.D., Wilson, D., Dal Grande, E. et al. (2000). Suicidal ideation in a random community sample: attributable risk due to depression and psychosocial and traumatic events. *Aust NZJ Psychiatry, 34*, pp. 98-106.

Internet Haber. (2016, April 08). Yediği dayağa dayanamadı intihar etti. Retrieved October 04, 2020, from <https://www.internethaber.com/yedigi-dayaga-dayanamadi-intihar-etti-1582890h.htm>

İran'da yine taşlanarak öldürülecek bir kadın. (2010, July 02). Retrieved October 04, 2020, from <https://www.cnnturk.com/2010/dunya/07/02/iranda.yine.taslanarak.oldurulecek.bir.kadin/582063.0/index.html>

İran'da 4 kadına kezzaplı saldırı. (2014, September 21). Retrieved September 28, 2020, from https://www.bbc.com/turkce/multimedya/2014/10/141020_iran_asitli_saldiri

İran'da recm hakkında yazan yazara hapis cezası. (2016, October 07). Retrieved October 04, 2020, from <https://www.sozcu.com.tr/2016/dunya/son-dakika-iranda-recm-hakkinda-yazan-yazara-hapis-cevasi-1432936/>

Özgecan'ın babasından Nihat Doğan'a çok sert sözler. (2018, April 03). Retrieved October 04, 2020, from <https://www.sozcu.com.tr/hayatim/magazin-haberleri/ozgecanin-babasindan-nihat-dogana-cok-sert-sozler/>

Kadınlarla Dayanışma Vakfı (KADAV). (n.d.). Retrieved September 29, 2020, from <http://www.siginaksizbirdunya.org/tr/biz-kimiz/kurultay-bilesenleri/37-kadınlarla-dayanisma-vakfi-kadav>

Karamustafaloğlu, O., & Yumrukçal, H. (2011). Depresyon ve anksiyete bozuklukları. *Şişli Etfal Hastanesi Tıp Bülteni*, 45, pp. 65-74.

Kahraman, L. (2014). İranlı Kadınların Toplumsal ve Siyasal Profili. *Sosyoloji Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 17(2), pp. 72-120.

Karanisoğlu, H. & Oskay, Ü. (1995) Kadına uygulanan şiddet (Hırpalanmış kadın). *Hemşirelik Bülteni. Florance Nightingale HYO Dergisi*. 9(37), pp. 93-97.

Özgen, F., & Aydın, H. (1999). Travma Sonrası Stres Bozukluğu. *Klinik Psikiyatri*, pp. 34-41.

Maercker A (Ed) (2005) *Therapie der posttraumatischen Belastungsstörungen*, 2nd ed. Berlin. Springer, pp. 3-51.

O'Brian, L.S. (Ed) (1998). *Traumatic events and mental health*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Öykümüz. (2013, March 27). Retrieved September 28, 2020, from <https://morcati.org.tr/tr/oykumuz/>

ÖKDM Bucalı kadınlara psikolojik ve hukuki destek veriyor. (2019, December 11). Retrieved October 04, 2020, from <https://ekmekvegul.net/gundem/okdm-bucali-kadınlara-psikolojik-ve-hukuki-destek-veriyor>

Özaydınlık, Y. D. (2015). Toplumsal Cinsiyet Temelinde Türkiye'de Kadın ve Eğitim. *Sosyal Politika Çalışmaları Dergisi*, 33, pp. 93-112. doi:10.21560/spcd.03093

Parlaktuna, İ. (2010). Türkiye'de Cinsiyete Dayalı Mesleki Ayrımcılığın Analizi. *Türkiye'de Cinsiyete Dayalı Mesleki Ayrımcılığın Analizi*, pp. 1217-1230.

Russell, D. (1984). *Sexual Exploitation: Rape, Child Sexual Abuse, and Workplace Harassment*, Washington, D.C., US Dept of Health and Human Services, pp. 245-62.

Roy, A. (2001). Childhood trauma and suicidal behavior in male cocaine dependent patients. *Suicide Life Threat Behav*, 31, pp. 194-196.

Statham, D. J., Heath, A. C., Madden, P. A., et al. (1998). Suicidal behaviour: An epidemiological and genetic study. *Psychol Med*, 28, pp. 839-855.

Spurrell, M. T., Mc Farlanen, A. C. (1995). Life-events and psychiatric symptoms in a general psychiatry clinic. The role of intrusion and avoidance. *Br J Med Psychol*, 68, pp. 333-340.

Sungur, M. Z. (1999). Ýkincil Travma ve Sosyal Destek. Retrieved September 30, 2020, from https://www.journalagent.com/kpd/pdfs/KPD_2_2_105_108.pdf.

Sevgilisini döven erkeđi engellemek isterken öldüren Kadir Şeker'e destek için Twitter'da kampanya. (2020, February 08). Retrieved September 28, 2020, from <https://www.bbc.com/turkce/haberler-turkiye-51427492>

Tipi, Y., & Tipi, G. (2019, November 09). 'Mavi Kız' kendini yaktı. Retrieved September 28, 2020, from <https://www.hurriyet.com.tr/dunya/mavi-kiz-kendini-yakti-41327384>

Türkçapar, H. (2004). Anksiyete Bozukluđu ve Depresyonun Tanısal ilişkileri. *Klinik Psikiyatri*, 12-16.

Van der Kolk B. A., Mc Farlane, A. C., Weisaeth, L. (Ed) (1996). *Traumatic Stress*. New York: Guilford.

Veith, I. (1977). Four Thousand Years of Hysteria, In Horowitz MJ, ed: *Hysterical Personality*, New York, Aronson, pp. 7-93.

Van der Kolk, B. A., Mc Farlane, A. C., Weisaeth, L. (Ed) (1996). *Traumatic Stress*. New York, Guilford.

Yüksel, Ş. (1996). *Tecavüz: iktidar amaçlı cinsel saldırıganlık: Evdeki Terör*. Yön Matb., Mor Çatı Yayınları, İstanbul. pp. 113-116.